

THE IMPORTANCE OF ACADEMIC VOCABULARY LIST

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Annotation. This thesis gives information about Academic Vocabulary List and the use of it in academic contexts. It is also stated the distinction of Academic Word List from Academic Vocabulary List. The thesis highlights exact numbers in its composition.

Key words. Academic Vocabulary List, Academic Word List and Academic Keyword list. These are suggested different researchers with different functions.

According to definition provided by Coxhead (2000), the Academic Word List is derived from a corpus that aims to capture the general academic vocabulary of English. It has had a significant historical impact on pedagogy and research. Coxhead (2000) divided over 3.500 million written words into 28 categories based on four fields: science, commerce, the arts, and law. 570 word families were arranged. Words are usually utilized in an academic context. Nagy and Townsend (2012) claimed that AWL can be utilized by students who learn or work independently in college or university courses.

It is necessary here to clarify exactly what is meant by Academic Vocabulary List and state the differences from other vocabulary lists. A 120 million-word in academic sub-corpus of the Corpus of Contemporary American serves as the foundation for the Academic Vocabulary List (Gardner & Davies, 2014). The nine subjects are covered by the sub-corpus that come from newspapers' finance sections, academic magazines, and academic journals.

In many significant ways, this list differs from Coxhead's (2000) influential Academic Word List (AWL). It is based on a larger, more diverse corpus. This is a significant advancement because the AWL has been widely criticized for its skew toward particular subject areas and the small size of corpus it was based on (Durrant, 2014).

The AVL is constructed using lemmas rather than word families, which consist of headwords and their inflectionally and derivationally related forms. Nation (2001) notes that understanding a headword is likely to facilitate comprehension of derivationally related forms and this justifies the decision to make the AWL a list of word families. According to Durrant et. al. (2009), this is a dubious assumption because word families frequently combine forms with very different meanings (for instance, the AWL item constitute encompasses constituting, constituent, and unconstitutional). However, Schmitt & Zimmerman (2002) argues that it is often difficult for students to able to make connections between even relatively related forms, and Gardner (2008), Hyland and Tse (2007) add to this point that the conflation of such items has been seen as a significant weakness of the list. Therefore, the AVL shows lemmas rather than word families (headwords plus inflectionally-related forms only).

The next term Academic Keyword List (AKL) is created by Magali Paquot, which contains 233 verbs, 180 adjectives, 87 adverbs, and 75 other words. AKL is completely different from AWL because it includes common words that have been shown to be important for structuring academic prose (Wessels, 2011). The AKL is reasonable for educators and researchers who use it for instructing content, research papers or purposes (Nushi, & Jenabzadeh, 2016).

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